

**THE ROLE OF CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM IN DEVELOPMENT OF
STUDENTS' SPECIALTIES IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTIONS**

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Abstract. This scientific article provides information about the credit-module system and the role of the credit-module system in development of students' specialties in Technical higher education institutions.

Key words: credit module, engineering, higher education, personnel, semester, labor, specialist, student, cargo.

Introduction: Today, it is considered an important task to train people working in all fields to become well-educated and mature professionals. And that puts a lot of responsibility on higher education institutions. Therefore, it is important for higher education institutions to use modern teaching methods so that students can become knowledgeable and mature professionals in their field. Improving the knowledge of students studying in the field of technology will also lead to the development of modern technology and engineering in our country. Today, all conditions are created in our country for the development of technical fields. In order to accelerate the development of this work in the field, the system of training in universities that provide personnel in the field of technology is gradually being transferred to the credit-module system.

The first step in the process of transition to the credit-modular system of higher education is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" Gradual transition of the educational process in educational institutions to the credit-module system, the introduction of advanced standards of higher education based on international experience, practical training in education aimed at gaining theoretical knowledge in the curriculum Gradual transition to a system of education aimed at the formation of skills, raising the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level. In order to further improve the organization of training, taking into account the best practices of higher education institutions of our country and abroad, to ensure a decent level of professional relations, to expand

their worldview and knowledge, to encourage self-study. It was emphasized that it consists in creating conditions for the strengthening of [1]. Following this decree, work is underway to gradually transfer the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a credit-module system.

Following the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" [2] In the system of lim, a large process of transition of the educational process to the credit-module system has begun. Initially, from the 2020-2021 academic year, 2 to 33 higher education institutions were transferred to the credit-module system. The purpose of the transition to a credit-modular system of higher education is the first 1000 and 500 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Nigher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities). inclusion in the list of institutions and ensuring the membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Bologna Declaration [4].

The main part: So what is the credit-module system of education?

Let's answer the above questions:

Credit is a measure of the student's workload (time) spent studying and mastering a subject in a particular field of study or program. A credit is a statutory minimum amount of time that a student is required to study in an auditorium and independently for one week. The credit is given to the student after completing the assignments in a particular subject and passing the final exam. Each student must collect credits in order to receive a diploma in their chosen field and specialty in the future. Accumulated credit will help the student to improve his / her skills or get a higher education throughout his / her life. In economic terms, the accumulated credit becomes the student's academic "asset" [6].

A module is a part of a curriculum that covers several subjects and courses. It is a set of several courses aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills, analytical and logical observation. According to foreign experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The disciplines included in the module are easily formed from complex theoretical to practical sciences, and logically complementary [5].

To further increase the knowledge of students studying in the field of technology, it is desirable to introduce a new method of teaching, ie "Credit-module" system of teaching to ensure their competitiveness in the labor market.

In this system, in contrast to the traditional system of education (for technical universities, where the credit-module system is not established), in the credit-module system of education, in addition to compulsory subjects, there are elective subjects and individual student schedules. 'ladi. Students will not be expelled or dropped out of class. If a student fails to get the required credits, he / she will have to retake the exam in the same subject. Higher education diplomas are issued only after the completion of the required credits. At the end of the semester, 50 percent of the students' grades are set by the science teacher and 50 percent by the university administration. That is, during the semester, the midterms, homework, and practical (laboratory) work are evaluated by the faculty. The final control will be taken by the university administration. Science teachers will not participate.

In order to collect credits, students are required to attend classes, complete assignments on time, and demonstrate their level of knowledge. High-achieving students can study independent work topics and submit them ahead of time. This saves time for future professionals. Those who get rid of the "burden" will spend the rest of the time in practice until the end of the semester. For example, a student must earn 30 credits per semester (60 per academic year). He received 8 credits in the field of "Manufacture and repair of cars", of which 4 credits will be collected from lectures, and the remaining 4 credits will be collected from practical training. If he fails to master the subject of "Manufacturing and Repair of Automobiles", he will be given the opportunity to retake the subject during the holidays. But this opportunity is paid. The cost of one loan is determined by dividing the total amount of tuition accumulated during the academic year by the amount of credits. For example, if the payment is 10,500,000 soums, this number is divided by 60. The resulting unit (175,000) is the cost of one loan. So, if we multiply this section by the credit for the subject "Manufacture and repair of cars" - 8, we get the cost of retraining (1,400,000). For this amount, he can re-study and pass the subject "Manufacture and repair of cars" and collect the necessary units of credit.

In this system, even those who are admitted on the basis of a state grant, if they are not able to collect the required credits in the specified subjects, they will be able to collect the required credits by paying a fixed amount to apply for a loan in which subject they could not collect. Of course, no one wants to overpay. Apparently, this system requires each student to work on himself, to complete assignments on time. In the traditional system, students have a large number of subjects to study, as well as a lot of theoretical lessons, and students spend a lot

of time in classrooms. At the same time, students face many difficulties due to lack of time to prepare for science assignments. In the credit-module system of education, the subjects are reduced and mainly focused on specialization. The lessons are 50% theoretical (in the classroom) and 50% practical, independent study. This shows that students have more time to prepare independently for the subjects. Allows students to complete homework assignments on time. In developed countries, the credit-module system of education is proving to be effective. The introduction of this system in universities specializing in technical areas will improve the quality of teaching, ensure transparency, reveal the true knowledge of the student and allow the student to study independently, work on themselves, acquire knowledge. . The use of credit-modular system of technical education will certainly help to increase the prestige of the university, so that students graduating from technical universities will not face any difficulties in finding a place in the labor market. This, of course, indicates that there will be a lot of offers in the labor market for students of technical universities, and that they will become mature professionals in the future.

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